

VETERINARY SANITARY MEASURES IN RABBIT FARMING

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ABSTRACT

It is very important to develop the rabbit breeding sector, grow nutritious meat, develop rabbit products in a cluster method, and carry out veterinary sanitary preventive measures. This article describes the implementation of preventive measures in the development of rabbit breeding.

Rabbit breeding is an important and fast-growing branch of animal husbandry. Currently, the production of rabbit meat is 4 million tons, and 70% of the total production of rabbit meat is in China, Italy, France and Spain. Including 660,000 tons of rabbit meat in China, 330,000 tons in Italy, 250,000 tons in France, 180,000 tons in Spain, and 15,000 tons in Russia. At present, about 100 agricultural farms have been established in our Republic.

Rabbit breeds are imported from Italy, Spain and Russia. "Damask rabbit" breeds were brought from Spain and "White New Zealand" breeds from the specialized Italian company "Martini". Including "Nurlus" rabbits from the Republic of Belarus were brought and distributed to livestock farmers of our Republic. On February 21-22, 2019, for the first time, bred rabbits rabbit exhibition was

organized Linear dimensions and absolute values of coccyx during postnatal ontogeny of gray rabbits There are Uzbeks in our country In connection with the establishment of the rabbit breeders' association (certificate No. 859 of the Ministry of Justice of December 12, 2018), the development of the rabbit breeding industry is defined as the solution of legal and legitimate interests. Wild rabbits are found in many areas. Wild hares graze in pairs or spread out at night. Honaki rabbits differ from their wild ancestors in many ways. They are superior in terms of economic benefits, such as live weight, meatiness, quick maturation, quality of wool coat. Rabbits become sexually and physically mature at 3-4 months of age. The gestation period of a female rabbit lasts 29-31 days. According to the production,

rabbits are divided into 3 types: meat, meat-skin (fur) and wool rabbits.

Rabbits are kept mostly in cages in multi-sector farms. Rabbits in cages are kept outdoors all year round. In winter, they are transferred to clean, bright, well-ventilated buildings. The cages are placed in two rows, 2, 4 rows.

An isolator for sick rabbits will be built and there will be cages for keeping rabbits separately. Cages are always disinfected with 10% hot alkali solution or 1% formalin solution. Metal cages are disinfected using a special flame.

Cages for pregnant rabbits are mechanically cleaned, disinfected and adapted. Watering and feeding bowls are placed inside the cages. The floor of the cage of young rabbits is made of 2x2 cm stainless wire mesh, and every 6-7 days, bedding is placed.

Mats must be present in the cages of pregnant rabbits and young rabbits. As a result of scientific research, in order to absorb urine and various gases into the rabbit cages, the corn starch separated from the grain is ground into a powder, placed in a gauze and placed in the shape of a 40x40 plate in the cages. Scientific research results were obtained (A.K.Turdiyev, O'.A.Rakhmonov 2021).

Bedding absorbs moisture. If it is changed every day, the baby rabbits will be kept warm. We can use wood shavings (sawdust), chopped soybean seeds as bedding. Every day, rabbit droppings are cleaned and put into special bags and used as fertilizer.

Hygiene of raising baby rabbits. Rabbits are born in unheated indoor facilities. The feathers of the first-born rabbits are plucked and placed in nests made for rabbits. Older mother rabbits do this on

their own. Rabbits must always be provided with clean water after birth and before birth. If there is a lack of water in the rabbit's body, the nutrition of minerals and vitamins will be disturbed, and they will eat their children. Newborn rabbits weigh up to 100 g, double in 6 days and 10 times in one month. The reason for this is the presence of up to 15% protein, 10-20% fat, sugar and 2.5% minerals in the milk of mother rabbits. Rabbits nurse their young with such milk for up to 20 days. No nutrient can replace it. When building rabbit hutches, protection from sunlight should be considered. Rabbits can't stand the heat. When the day gets too hot, they can get sunburned. Rabbits need a lot of oxygen. Rabbits in cages will suffer from poor air circulation in buildings. Rabbits tolerate the cold easily, they feel good in the open air even in severe winter. In some cases, we should not let the rabbits freeze.

The linear dimensions and absolute values of the weight of the humerus in the postnatal ontogenesis of rabbits of the gray In the article: in the treatment of keratoconus conjunctivitis in calves, in addition to traditional methods, when 3 ml of auto blood and 3 ml of 0.5% novocaine solution were injected under the skin of the eyelids of the affected eyes, the morphological changes in their blood

In the article: In the article, the etiopathogenesis of purulent conjunctivitis caused by conjunctivitis and its complications, methods of treatment with novocaine siege, execution methods and economic efficiency are shown.

The ratio of natural light for rabbits should be 1:3, 1:5, 1:8 in buildings, 1:10, 1:12 in tanneries. Temperature +14+20°C, humidity 60-80%, artificial lighting 20 lux, air movement 0.3 m/s, ammonia 0.01 m

g/l, carbon dioxide should not exceed 0.20%. Special sun-proof devices on the cages to prevent the rabbits from getting overheated and sunburned created. (Kh.B. Yunusov A.K. Turdiyev, O`A. Rahmonov 2021).

Conclusions.

- Rabbit farms should be surrounded by green trees

- When entering the rabbit hutches, dizomat and dizobar should be at the required level.

- It is advisable to carry out prophylactic measures in rabbit houses, i.e. disinfection, disinsection, deratization, deworming in a timely manner.

- Giving rabbits hydroponically grown grass (wheat, barley, corn, soybeans) increases the productivity of rabbits.

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